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Recommendations on Adapted Integrative Forest Management

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1. Introduction

Climate change has become a main driver of environmental change, leading to an increase in mean global temperatures and a more frequent occurrence of extreme weather events, while cold extremes have become less common. In Europe, the mean annual temperature has risen by more than 1.1°C since the preindustrial period, being south-western, central and north-eastern Europe and alpine regions the most affected.

Forest owners and managers in Europe have always dealt with future uncertainty, as biotic and abiotic risks have historically affected forestry decisions as well as future wood market uncertainty. In this sense, active adaptive forest management through silviculture is the technical response to the observed and expected impacts that climate change has on forests. The consideration of the constraints posed by new and future climatic conditions in silvicultural practices should be gradually implemented in the different forest systems.

Adaptive forest management produces feedback of silvicultural interventions and management aims, joined to the background of changing environments and varying owners' perspectives .

Thus, it represents a flexible forest management that considers small-scale variations of climate and site conditions. At a larger scale, there is a need to identify and to implement policy and management responses that can help integrate different demands and objectives and anticipate and prepare for future climate scenarios.

Throughout this text we will learn about some of these silvicultural interventions.

2. Impacts of climate change on forests

The IPCC projections outline scenarios suggesting that in the medium term, large forested areas could be affected by new climatic conditions. Rising temperatures could cause an increase in potential evapotranspiration (PET) in vegetation. As a consequence, the water deficit will necessarily increase, leading to a trend towards greater aridity depending on the region. Thus, forests need to adapt to changing environmental conditions in order to remain stable and to continue the provision of multiple ecosystem goods and services (e.g. biodiversity, wood products, non-wood products, habitats conservation, recreation, landscape protection, carbon sequestration potential, etc).

The expected impacts include, among others:

- Displacement and migration of forest species due to changes in environmental conditions.
- Processes of species extinction and substitution.
- Increase in decline processes (reduced growth, loss of vegetative vigor, defoliation, mortality, etc.) associated with drought events and occurrences of extreme summer temperatures.
- The activity of pests and pathogens may be favored by new environmental conditions and the longer duration of the growing season.
- Increase in abiotic disturbances, such as wildfires or windthrow events.
- Changes in the net primary productivity of forests, which, in some sites, may become carbon emitters.
- Episodes of decline and mortality in different species.
- Regeneration bottlenecks for species in their most southern distribution.
- Upward shift of the forest altitudinal limit.
- Phenological changes in the species, for example, extension of the vegetative period in broadleaf species, caused by an earlier budburst and a delayed leaf fall.
- Changes in the provision of ecosystem services.

For example, different models predict that under unfavorable climate scenarios (e.g., RCP 8.5), the previously mentioned impacts will worsen. Observable phenomena such as species displacement, replacement, and extinction are expected, along with severe losses in growth and productivity, widespread failures in the natural regeneration of certain species, reductions in the provision of ecosystem services, and increased severity and spatial extent of pest outbreaks.

3. Principles of active adaptive forest management

An active adaptive forest management should include different silvicultural interventions aimed at: (i) reducing the vulnerability of forests to the impacts of the new climatic conditions; and (ii) enhancing the resilience and adaptive capacity of forests, while ensuring its persistence under the new climates scenarios. Based on these two general ideas, adaptation-oriented silviculture establishes a series of principles that translate into specific practices.

3.1. Natural-oriented forest management

Adaptive forest management must not ignore the autonomous adaptation processes inherent to forest ecosystems, but rather should support and leverage them. Research should be promoted to identify genotypes and provenances with higher tolerance to the most probable or severe future climate scenarios, so that better-adapted material is available in case such impacts occur. This approach faces two-fold uncertainty: (1) the future site conditions, and (2) the capability of the selected species to perform as expected. While this approach should still be

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considered with caution in native-species reforestation programs, it may be highly relevant for planning high-productivity forest crops or plantations for biomass production.

A quick alternative might be to include clonal banks and provenance trials established in the past into tree breeding programs in order to identify drought-resistant genotypes and provenances, those with better recovery capacity after extreme climate events, or those with greater phenotypic plasticity and autonomous adaptive capacity.

Another option to consider is to promote and accelerate the migration of species or provenances through assisted migration, toward habitats where they are likely to be more competitive under future climate scenarios. These practices involve moving seeds and/or juvenile or adult propagules within the species' current geographic range, at its edge, or even into new areas. In this last case, the goal is to find habitats that compensate for the expected climate impacts in their original locations.

Adaptation-oriented forest management should also take advantage of the natural dynamics of regeneration and species replacement. Natural regeneration represents one of the key bottlenecks for the persistence of forest systems, a challenge that will worsen under climate change scenarios.

3.2. Increasing intra- and interspecific biodiversity

Species diversity operates on two fronts: on the one hand, mixed forests are more resistant to disturbances caused by droughts or storms and are more likely to recover quickly after catastrophic events than monospecific forests. In this regard, it is worth noting that many forest pests exhibit a high degree of specificity toward the species they attack. Consequently, large monospecific stands — as is the case with many afforestations — are more susceptible to pests than mixed stands.

On the other hand, a broad genetic and species base allows for greater adaptive capacity in the face of climatic changes, as it increases the range of ecological conditions compatible with the presence of forest cover. Similarly, high intra- and interspecific diversity enables the natural selection of individuals best adapted to new conditions.

3.3. Increasing structural diversity

This principle is based on the differing degrees of susceptibility or vulnerability that groups of different size or age have to biotic or abiotic agents. Droughts and early or late frosts may have a greater impact on individuals in the juvenile development phase, while windstorms and heavy snowfalls tend to affect taller trees more severely, particularly in relation to slenderness. The presence of a mature tree layer can improve the development conditions of understory individuals (both of the same and different species) through the well-known "nurse effect".

3.4. Increasing individual resistance to biotic and abiotic agents

Adaptive forest management aims at reducing vulnerability, while increasing the adaptive capacity of forest species to the most limiting stress factor. For this purpose, individual trees must reach its highest potential for growth and development, thus attaining maximum vigor.

This greater vigor makes individuals less susceptible to pathogen attacks at low to moderate infestation levels (which typically target the most weakened trees), and more resistant to stressful climate episodes. Increasing individual vigor could imply a reduction in standing volume, which in turn decreases the risk of damage during extreme events or disturbances, making them more resistant to wind, snow, and other physical stressors.

3.5. Promoting or accelerating changes in structure or species

The increase in water deficit and a decrease in net primary productivity can reduce tree vigor, triggering phenomena of decline and/or mass mortality, often associated with the interaction of drought and pathogens. This situation can be especially critical in areas where vegetation is already at the edge of its habitable range. From an adaptive perspective, structural and species

changes should be proactively encouraged, including the introduction of species and progenies better suited to a projected range of future conditions.

However, in some regions, the species represent the last stage of arboreal vegetation before being replaced by shrubland. Therefore, if preserving a tree canopy is considered necessary, the introduction of drought-resistant provenances—or even non-native species—might be considered. In any case, species or provenances must be selected in such a way that they allow for a gradual replacement under changing scenarios, rather than a displacement of the original species or provenances under current conditions.

3.6. Making silviculture more flexible, diversified, and site-specific

Implementing adaptive forest management requires increased flexibility in the scheduling of silvicultural interventions. In this context, classical forest management concepts (rotation period, intervention planning, allowable cuttings) become less central. Instead, there is a stronger focus on applying silviculture that is much more spatially and temporally localized and that is flexible enough to respond to a wide and uncertain range of future climatic conditions (proactive adaptation silviculture). The goal of such silviculture is to guide forest stands toward a condition that is compatible with a broad range of potential future states.

4. Practical application of the principles of adaptive forest management

This section presents examples of how adaptive forest management can be applied.

4.1. Reduction of standing volume

The abandonment of traditional agricultural practices, combined with nearly absent silvicultural management, has led to a significant accumulation of biomass in recent decades. These situations result in excessive stand density, which inevitably reduces individual tree vigor due to increased competition for water resources, thereby increasing susceptibility to decline during drought episodes and higher vulnerability to wildfires. Reducing standing volume should be done cautiously in older stands, as it increases susceptibility to windthrow.

4.2. Regeneration cuttings

In the most xeric sites, where natural regeneration is the main bottleneck for the persistence of the forest, the protection of young seedlings becomes particularly important. Small changes in microclimatic conditions have repeatedly could cause the failure of natural regeneration efforts. Ensuring the survival of natural regeneration usually requires the retention of a greater number of adult trees to provide shelter.

Therefore, the trend is toward promoting greater structural irregularity in forest stands, along with a gradual reduction in the area occupied by even-aged stands resulting from natural regeneration.

4.3. Promotion of mixed stands

Mixed stands exhibit greater stability. The forest productivity of the main species is not negatively affected by the presence of other coexisting species, if its share is maintained within a limit. This is due to the differentiated use of resources — such as differences in root system architecture and development, or variations in vegetative periods. This effect is particularly notable when the mixed species differ significantly in terms of ecophysiology, as in pine–broadleaf mixtures.

4.4. Afforestation and reforestation

Species selection is a key aspect in reforestation and afforestation projects. Choosing the right species requires a thorough analysis of soil and climate conditions to determine which species—and which provenances within those species—are best adapted to the edaphoclimatic parameters. However, historical climate data, which are collected from meteorological stations, do not reflect the climate of the coming decades—the conditions under which the newly established forest will actually develop.

Therefore, taking future climate scenarios into account is essential, and may lead to the selection of more xerophilous species than those indicated under past climatic conditions. A

second important consideration is the need to zone the territory and promote species diversity in reforestation efforts, selecting species at a scale smaller than the forest stand, and using ecological criteria (such as humidity, topography, and soil characteristics).

Finally, reforestation projects should incorporate techniques that optimize the use of the limiting resource—water—again applying such techniques at a scale smaller than the stand.

4.5. Localization and Flexibility of Management

The selection of a silvicultural approach for a stand should be made not only by observing its current characteristics (site quality, stand structure, density, etc.) but also by taking into account future climatic conditions that may have a decisive influence. Despite their inherent uncertainty, future climate scenarios must be a fundamental element in the design of silviculture.

5. Final remarks

It is important to note that mitigation is not adaptation. Mitigation and adaptation to climate change are concepts that are often mixed up. Mitigation is defined as the set of human interventions aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions and/or enhancing the absorption capacity of carbon sinks. Forests are one of the main natural carbon sinks—and practically the only ones currently subject to active management.

From the forestry sector's perspective, management for mitigation focuses on modifying practices to increase forest area, reduce deforestation and forest degradation, enhance carbon sequestration and storage capacity in forests, extend the lifespan of forest products that serve as carbon reservoirs, and promote the substitution of fossil fuels with forest-based biomass

The strategic role forests can play in climate change mitigation has led to a growing interest in mitigation policies, often pushing adaptation into the background. In some cases, actions presented as adaptation have actually been practices focused on mitigation. In this regard, while forests are being asked to increase their carbon sequestration capacity—and do so in longer-lived carbon pools—a basic principle is often forgotten: we must adapt our forests to new environmental conditions if we are to achieve mitigation goals. Forests not managed with adaptation in mind may decline, becoming net carbon emitters, and may suffer from reduced productivity and individual growth capacity, thereby weakening their role as long-term carbon sinks.

The core issue is that management strategies optimized for mitigation are not necessarily optimal—or even viable—when it comes to ensuring the adaptation of forest systems.

6. Recommendations for Implementation

Throughout this chapter, the main principles of adaptive forest management have been presented. Characterizing a silviculture approach for adapting a forest to climate change requires knowledge, monitoring, and assessment of possible impacts, as well as the definition of critical thresholds that trigger the implementation of measures.

A second key aspect is defining management objectives in terms of ecosystem services (productive, protective, environmental, social, etc.) to ensure that the adaptation silviculture designed will guarantee their provision.

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When designing or adapting proposed adaptive measures, the inherent characteristics of the species must be considered (shade tolerance, water or nutrient requirements, seed dispersal methods, sprouting capacity, etc.) as well as the species' potential responses to expected scenarios of temperature and water regime changes.

Finally, any silvicultural proposal for adaptation must be supported by modifications to current practices and continuous monitoring of the effects of these practices, following the principles of adaptive Forest management.

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